

Condensation of Azeloyl Chloride and Sebasoyl Chloride with Di- and Polyhydric Phenols, their Methyl Ethers and Halogenated Derivatives

D. CHAKRAVARTI & (MRS.) MINATI SAHA

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-9

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Azeloyl Chloride and Sebasoyl Chloride have been condensed with resorcinol, resorcinol monomethyl ether, resorcinol dimethyl ether, 4-chloro resorcinol, 4-chloro resorcinol dimethyl ether, veratrole, pyrogallol trimethyl ether, 4-bromo resorcinol, 4-bromo resorcinol dimethyl ether in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride producing 1,9 diones and 1,10 diones respectively.

Chakravarti and Chakravarti¹ reported the condensation of azeloyl chloride and sebasoyl chloride with various monohydric phenols and their ethers in presence of aluminium chloride.

In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of azeloyl chloride and sebasoyl chloride with various di- and polyhydric phenols, their methyl ethers and halogenated derivatives.

The condensation of the above dibasic acid dichlorides with resorcinol, resorcinol monomethyl ether, resorcinol dimethyl ether, 4-chloro resorcinol, 4-chloro resorcinol dimethyl ether, veratrole, pyrogallol trimethyl ether, 4-bromo resorcinol, 4-bromo resorcinol dimethyl ether has been found to occur at 0°-5° in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and nitrobenzene or tetrachloroethane as solvent leading to the formation of diaryl diketones (I) in good yield together with some aryl keto acids (II) in small quantity and this serves as an excellent method for the synthesis of aromatic 1 : 9 and 1 : 10 diketones.

where $n = 7, 8$.

In all these condensation reactions the acyl group is found to enter without any exception the position which has the maximum directive influence of the hydroxy or the alkoxy groups.

The constitution of the products is established by their oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate to the corresponding β -resorcylic acid derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

1,9 bis-(2,4 dihydroxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione (I, $R = R_2 = OH$; $R_1 = R_3 = H$; $n = 7$): A solution of freshly distilled resorcinol (4.4 g) in nitrobenzene (25 ml.) was taken in a three necked flask (250 ml.) equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride guard tube. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (8 g.) was added to this solution after cooling it to 0° . A solution of azeloyl chloride (4.5 g.) in nitrobenzene (10 ml.) was taken in the dropping funnel and added dropwise in course of about 1 hr, with stirring. The stirring was continued for a further period of about 4 hrs at room temperature and the mixture was left at this temperature overnight. After decomposing with ice and hydrochloric acid the reaction product was steam distilled to remove the nitrobenzene. The crude product that solidified on cooling was filtered, washed with water and treated with $NaHCO_3$ solution. The insoluble residue was collected by filtration, washed with water and finally purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol. It crystallised as colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 115° , yield 2.5 g. (Found : C, 67.38; H, 6.32; $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 67.74; H, 6.45%).

The alcoholic solution of the diketone produced a violet colouration with ferric chloride solution.

The dioxime was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 217° . (Found : N, 6.70; $C_{21}H_{28}O_6N_2$ requires N, 6.96%).

The structure of the above diketone was confirmed thus: (a) On methylation of the above diketone with dimethyl sulphate and alkali, a product was obtained which was identified as 1,9 bis (2,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, a diketone which is also obtained from the condensation of resorcinol dimethyl ether and azeloyl chloride. 1,9 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate yielded β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether.

The compounds obtained from other phenols and phenolic ethers, prepared in the same way are described in Table I. The compounds prepared with sebasoyl chloride are described in Table II.

TABLE I
Condensation of Di- and Polyhydric Phenols, their Methyl Ethers and Halogenated Derivatives with Azeloyl Chloride

Phenols & Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Reqd. %		
1. Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene)	a) 1,9 bis-(2,4-dihydroxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, m.p. 116° (dil. ethanol); reported m.p. 114° [Rybakova & Zilberman; <i>Zhur Otschet Kbiin</i> , 31, 1272, 1961].	$C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ (I, R=R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =R ₃ =H; n = 7)	C; 67.38 H; 6.32	67.74 Dioxime, m.p. 217° (dl. ethanol) 6.45 C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₂ requires N, 6.96%.	Methylation with dimethyl sulphate and alkali gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from resorcinol dimethyl ether and azeloyl chloride (m.p. and mixed m.p. 95°). Product developed a violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Infrared spectrum of the diketone ν max (cm ⁻¹); 3356, 3344, 3226, 1640, 1620, 1515, 880.	
2. Resorcinol Mono-methyl Ether (in nitrobenzene)	a) 1,9 bis-(2-hydroxy, 4-methoxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, m.p. 89° (ethanol)	$C_{23}H_{28}O_6$ (I, R=OH; R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H; n = 7).	C; 68.72 H; 6.84	69.00 Di(2 : 4 D.N.P.H.) m.p. 151° (glacial acetic acid) 7.00 (Found : N, 14.53; C ₂₃ H ₃₆ O ₁₂ N ₆ requires N, 14.74%).	A violet colouration obtained with FeCl ₃ solution.	
	b) ω -(2-hydroxy, 4-methoxy benzoyl)-octanoic acid, m.p. 110° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{16}H_{22}O_6$ (II, R = OH; R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 7).	C; 65.00 H; 7.20	65.31 7.48	A violet colouration obtained with FeCl ₃ solution.	
3. Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether	a) 1,9 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-nonane, 1,9 dione, m.p. 96° (dil. acetic acid).	$C_{25}H_{32}O_6$ (I, R=R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =R ₃ =H; n = 7).	C; 69.89 H; 7.28	70.09 7.48	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ gives β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether, (m.p. and mixed m.p. 107°). Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν max (cm ⁻¹); 1260, 1025, 1650, 1600, 1565, 842.	

TABLE I—Contd.

Phenols & Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Reqd. %		
4. 4-Chloro Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene)	a) 1,9 bis-(2,4-dihydroxy, 5-chloro phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, m.p. 157° (glacial acetic acid).	$C_{21}H_{22}O_5Cl_2$ (I, R=R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Cl; n = 7).	C; 57.32 H; 4.88	57.14 165-166° (dil. ethanol)	Dioxime, m.p. 165-166° (dil. ethanol) (Found: N, 5.47; $C_{21}H_{24}O_6N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 5.94%)	An intense violet colouration obtained with FeCl ₃ solution. Methylation of the diketone with dimethyl sulphate and alkali gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from 4-chloro resorcinol dimethyl ether and azeloyl chloride (identified by m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen; m.p. and mixed m.p. 145°). Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹); 3330; 1626, 1580, 1488, 880.
	b) ω -(2,4 dihydroxy, 5-chloro benzoyl)-octanoic acid, m.p. 126° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{15}H_{19}O_5Cl$ (II, R=R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Cl; n = 7).	C; 57.11 H; 6.26	57.23 6.04	—	
5. 4-Chloro Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,9 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy, 5-chloro phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, m.p. 147° (glacial acetic acid).	$C_{23}H_{30}O_6Cl_2$ (I, R=R ₂ =OCH ₃ ; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Cl; n = 7).	C; 60.28 H; 6.35	60.36 6.04	Dioxime, m.p. 140° (dil. ethanol) (Found: N, 5.13; $C_{23}H_{32}O_6N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 5.31%).	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Infrared spectrum (nujol), ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹); 1025, 1274, 1650, 1587, 1488, 833.
6. Pyrogallol Trimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	1,9 bis-(2-hydroxy, 3,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, m.p. 117° (ethanol), 117° reported m.p. 115° [Kichiro Kakemi <i>et al</i> ; <i>Yakugaku Zasshi</i> ; 86 , 778, 1966].	$C_{25}H_{32}O_8$ (I, R = OH; R ₁ =R ₂ =OMe; R ₃ =H; n = 7).	C; 65.05 H; 6.70	65.21 6.96	Di(2 : 4 D.N.P.H.) (Found: N, 13.41; $C_{37}H_{40}N_2O_{14}$ requires N, 13.66%).	A violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. The methoxyl group present in the diketone estimated by Ziesel's method. (Found: OCH ₃ , 27.01; C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₈ requires OCH ₃ , 26.95%).
7. 4-Bromo Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,9 bis-(2,4 dimethoxy 5-bromo phenyl)-nonane 1,9 dione, m.p. 160° (glacial acetic acid).	$C_{25}H_{30}O_6Br_2$ (I, R=R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Br; n = 7).	C; 50.95 H; 5.31	51.19 5.20	—	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ gave 5-bromo- β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether, m.p. 194° (mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen, 194°).

TABLE II
Condensation of Di- and Polyhydric Phenols, their Methyl Ethers and Halogenated Derivatives with Sebasoyl Chloride

Phenols & Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Reqd. %		
1. Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,10-bis-(2,4-dihydroxy phenyl)-decane, 1,10 dione, m.p. 171° (glacial acetic acid); reported m.p. 172° [Rybakova and Zilberman; <i>Zhair Obschei Khim</i> , 31, 1275, 1961]	$C_{22}H_{26}O_6$ (I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 8).	C; 68.23 H; 6.59	68.59 6.74	Di-(2 : 4 D.N.P.H.), (Found : N, 14.68; C ₃₄ H ₃₄ O ₁₂ N ₈ requires N, 15.01%).	Methylation with dimethyl sulphate and alkali gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from resorcinol dimethyl ether and sebasoyl chloride, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample 126°. A violet colouration obtained with FeCl ₃ solution.
2. Resorcinol Mono-methyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2-hydroxy,4-methoxy phenyl)-decane 1,10 dione, m.p. 122° (ethanol).	$C_{24}H_{30}O_6$ (I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 8).	C; 69.19 H; 7.42	69.56 7.25	Di-(2 : 4 D.N.P.H.), (Found : N, 14.18; C ₃₆ H ₃₆ O ₁₂ N ₈ requires N, 14.47%).	A violet colouration obtained with FeCl ₃ solution.
3. Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-decane 1,10 dione, m.p. 128° (dil. acetic acid). Reported m.p. 127° [Paul Schlack & Walter Kollar; <i>Ger.</i> , 711, 1086, 1960]	$C_{26}H_{34}O_6$ (I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 8).	C; 70.86 H; 8.05	70.60 7.69	Di-(2 : 4 D.N.P.H.), m.p. 137° (benzene); (Found : N, 13.41; C ₃₈ H ₄₂ O ₁₂ N ₈ requires N, 13.96)	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
4. 4-Chloro Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2,4-dihydroxy,5-chloro phenyl)-decane 1,10 dione, m.p. 202° (ethanol).	$C_{26}H_{24}O_6Cl_2$ (I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 8).	C; 57.89 H; 5.05	58.02 5.27	Dioxime, m.p. 171-172° (dil. ethanol).	Methylation with dimethyl sulphate and alkali gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from 4-chloro resorcinol dimethyl ether and sebasoyl chloride, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen 157°. The diketone developed a violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
5. 4-Chloro Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy,5-chloro phenyl)-decane 1,10 dione, m.p. 157° (ethanol).	$C_{28}H_{32}O_6Cl_2$ (I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 8).	C; 60.85 H; 5.93	61.06 6.26	Di-(2 : 4 D.N.P.H.), m.p. 187° (benzene); (Found : N, 12.25; C ₃₈ H ₄₀ O ₁₂ N ₈ Cl ₂ requires N, 12.86%).	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.

TABLE II—Contd.

Phenols & Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Reqd. %		
6. Pyrogallol Trimethyl Ether, (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2-hydroxy, 3,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-decane, 1,10 dione, m.p. 126° (ethanol); reported m.p. 125° [Kiichiro Kakemi <i>et al</i> , <i>Yakugaku Zasshi</i> , 86(9), 778, 1966].	$C_{36}H_{34}O_8$ (I, R = OH; $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$; $R_3 = H$; $n = 8$).	C; 65.51 H; 6.93	65.83 7.17	—	The diketone developed a strong violet colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution. The methoxyl group estimated by Ziesel's method (Found: OCH_3 26.53; $C_{26}H_{24}O_8$ requires OCH_3 26.16%).
7. 4-Bromo Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2,4-dihydroxy 5-bromo phenyl)-decane 1,10 dione, m.p. 210° (glacial acetic acid).	$C_{22}H_{24}O_8Br_2$ (I, R = $R_2 = OH$; $R_1 = H$; $R_3 = Br$; $n = 8$).	C; 48.31 H; 4.26	48.53 4.41	Dioxime, m.p. 110° (dil. ethanol) (Found: N, 4.69; $C_{32}H_{28}O_6Br_2N_2$ requires N, 4.89%).	Methylation with dimethyl sulphate and alkali gave a product identical with the diketone obtained from 4-bromo resorcinol dimethyl ether and sebasoyl chloride, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen 173°. The diketone developed a strong violet colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution.
8. 4-Bromo Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	1,10 bis-(2,4 dimethoxy 5-bromo phenyl)-decane 1,10 dione, m.p., 173° (glacial acetic acid).	$C_{26}H_{32}O_8Br_2$ (I, R = $R_2 = OMe$; $R_1 = H$; $R_3 = Br$; $n = 8$).	C; 51.89 H; 5.14	52.00 5.33	Dioxime, m.p. 143° (dil. ethanol) (Found: N, 4.15; $C_{26}H_{34}O_6N_2Br_2$ requires N, 4.44%).	Oxidation with alkaline $KMnO_4$ gave 5-bromo β -resorecylic acid; dimethyl ether identified by its m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen (m.p. and mixed m.p. 196°). No characteristic colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution.

REFERENCES

1. D. Chakravarti and A. Chakravarti *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 743.